

POLICY BRIEF

Integrating Spatial Data for Credible, Just and Synergic Non-state and Transnational Climate and Biodiversity Action

Summary

Climate and biodiversity are inseparable, yet global action to address them remains divided. As countries and non-state actors ramp up pledges, analysis and monitoring often lack one essential ingredient: knowing where implementation actually happens. Without spatial data, we cannot see progress, verify impact, or ensure fair outcomes. A new commentary in *npj Climate Action* urges that climate and biodiversity tracking be rooted in place.

Context

Integrating **climate and biodiversity action** - especially by cities, companies, and communities - requires knowing *where* change happens. Yet, on prominent action platforms, such as the NAZCA portal, administered by the UN Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC), most actors and initiatives only report pledges, not locations. Without **spatial data**, we cannot assess real-world impacts, identify synergies, or ensure fairness. We highlight key arguments for spatialisation:

1. Spatial data enables multidimensional monitoring of climate and biodiversity outcomes

Spatial data captures where actions are implemented, allowing assessments that reflect local environmental, social, and economic contexts. This helps move beyond high-level goals toward verifying real on-the-ground impacts. It also makes it possible to identify synergies and avoid unintended trade-offs in climate and biodiversity interventions.

2. Spatial data supports comparison and learning across contexts and scales

Standardized, location-based measurements, such as those from remote sensing, enable consistent tracking of outcomes across regions. Spatial data can be linked to information on land use, ecosystem services, and socio-economic conditions to factor in contextual differences. This helps characterize and manage climate–biodiversity interlinkages across ecosystems and scales.

3. Spatial data can promote more just and inclusive outcomes

By situating climate and biodiversity action within specific geographies, spatial data highlights community realities, ecological sensitivities, and the presence of Indigenous or local territories. This creates opportunities for participatory data collection and decision-making that avoid past harms from exclusionary governance. When used equitably, spatial data can support environmental justice by informing fairer distribution of benefits, risks, and resources.

4. Spatialisation strengthens collaboration across disciplines and sectors

Spatial data links ecological, social, and policy processes that are often treated separately, encouraging interdisciplinary cooperation. It also supports cross-sectoral planning by helping policymakers, practitioners, and communities co-design integrated responses. Improved

spatial visualizations further enhance communication and help translate research into effective action.

Recommendations

As the UNFCCC renews efforts to engage non-state actors in global climate and biodiversity action, and similar platforms under the Convention on Biological Diversity, and UN Convention Combating Desertification are implemented, they should require and support spatially explicit reporting to ensure effective implementation tracking. This will provide clear visibility into where change is happening, its effectiveness, and who bears costs and benefits, moving beyond simple pledges to concrete action on the ground. This would involve non-state and transnational actors providing simple location data, such as GPS coordinates or project polygons, to allow for integrated monitoring and enhance transparency and accountability for both climate and nature actions. With expanding georeferenced datasets, improved spatial analysis tools, and rapid advances in AI, there is a major opportunity to strengthen global monitoring and learning—though challenges such as uneven data access, limited technical capacity, and concerns about sharing location information still need to be addressed.

Key Messages

Reasons to integrate spatial data in climate & biodiversity action tracking

Spatial data enables **multidimensional monitoring** (beyond emissions)

Spatial data allows **contextual comparison and learning**

Spatial data can **drive justice and inclusion** through participatory mapping

Spatialisation fosters **collaboration across** disciplines, sectors, and communities

We urgently ask UNFCCC, CBD, & UNCCD Action Agendas to:

Require

spatial data in non-Party reporting

Enable

integration and joint monitoring

Provide

incentives, capacity building, & guidelines for gathering spatial data

Spatial data is not a technical add-on, it's essential infrastructure for credible, just, and synergistic climate-biodiversity action.

Read our full paper

Hagenström, P., Pettoirelli, N., Boran, I., Bridgewater, P., Delgado Pugley, D., Folkard-Tapp, H., Hsu, A., Imbach, P., Kok, M. T. J., VanDeveer, S. D., Widerberg, O., & Chan, S. (2025). *From pledges to places: Action agendas need spatial data to integrate climate and biodiversity action.* *Nature Portfolio Journal Climate Action*. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s44168-025-00307-5>

